

Full Length Research Paper

Knowledge, attitude and practice of farmers to avian influenza resurgence in Ibadan, Nigeria: A case study of the 2015 avian influenza resurgence

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Highly pathogenic avian influenza of the strain H5N1 has been noted as a deadly virus of poultry with the ability to affect humans. Chickens in Kano and Kaduna States in northern Nigeria were infested with diarrhea and exhibited respiratory distress, and thereafter died within a few days sometime in January 2006. An epidemiological questionnaire-based cross-sectional study design in a major live bird market in Ibadan was used for 206 farmers in order to capture their socio-demographic characteristics and determine the knowledge, attitude and practices (especially bio-security practices) that could predispose their farms to avian influenza outbreak. Attempts were also made to find the determinants of the avian influenza outbreak. This study proved that educated individuals were better informed about best practices and hence compliance with best bio-security practices would be ensured and/or guaranteed. The predictors of high AI knowledge among poultry farmers were age ($p = 0.01$),

education ($p = 0.05$), occupation ($p = 0.03$), No of birds present on the farm ($p = 0.05$), and years of farm establishment ($p = 0.05$). In this study, farms owned by older people were about 3 times more likely to experience outbreak because they may not have been aware of latest trends in managing farm bio-security. Those owned by males were about 2.5 times less likely because males have been proven to be quite energetic thereby allowing them to be able to discharge their duties with vigor. Also, farms owned by uneducated people and those without carcass disposal and quarantine facilities were about 5.4, 2.2, and 1.3 times more likely to suffer from an AI outbreak. Total refusal of some farmers to participate was a serious limitation. Farmers in Oyo State have good knowledge about the Avian Influenza.

Keywords: Avian influenza, Oyo state, poultry, resurgence, knowledge, attitude, practice

INTRODUCTION

Highly pathogenic avian influenza of the strain H5N1 has been noted as a deadly virus of poultry with the ability to affect humans (Webby, 2003; Guan, 2004). The backbone of the poultry industry in Nigeria is Oyo state (Ibirogba, 2015). Chickens in Kano and Kaduna States in northern Nigeria voided diarrhea and exhibited respiratory distress, and thereafter died within a few days sometime in January 2006 (Gardner *et al.*, 2007).

Resurgence of bird flu was reported and confirmed on a commercial farm and in a live bird market in Kano and Lagos States respectively on January 8, 2015 (Adesina FMARD, 2015). Seven states reported cases of the bird flu: Kano, Lagos, Ogun, Delta, Rivers, Edo and Plateau States. Thereafter, 21 commercial farms, 9 Live Bird Markets and one private zoo were affected in the seven states (Adesina FMARD, 2015).

A total of 140,390 birds were associated with avian influenza as at January 21, 2015, with 22,573 (16%) mortality recorded (Adesina FMARD, 2015).

Understanding knowledge, attitude and practices (KAP) of farmers to Avian Influenza would help in cost effective decision making processes by the government (Yakhshilikov *et al.*, 2011).

Despite the fact that many were aware of the devastating effects of highly pathogenic avian influenza, it did not deter farmers from continuing with sharp practices of breaching prevention and control of Avian Influenza outbreaks (Yakhshilikov *et al.*, 2011).

In an earlier study in Lagelu, Oyo state, Nigeria, it was found that majority of respondents (78.6%) were of the opinion that avian influenza was preventable despite the fact that they were aware of it being a deadly disease. A good number of them were aware of the risks evolved when the disease strikes. None of the farmers vaccinated their poultry against avian influenza (Fatiregun *et al.*, 2008).

Awareness of Avian Influenza has risen in recent years probably due to media exposure given to the disease (Lau *et al.*, 2008). The faeces of infected birds are usually laden with the avian influenza virus (Gauthier-Clerc *et al.*, 2007).

It is important to wash ones hands with soap after touching any poultry, egg or bird meat as a starting point of proper hygiene for prevention purposes (Sreta *et al.*, 2009). The study was embarked upon to know the Knowledge, attitude and practice of farmers to avian influenza in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

Study area

Oyo State, (8.000°N 4.000°E) covers approximately an area of 28,454 square kilometers and is ranked 14th by size. Agriculture is the main occupation of the people of Oyo state. Ibadan is located in South-western Nigeria. It is the capital of Oyo state. Its population is estimated to be about 3,800,000 according to 2006 estimates. The choice of Ibadan in Oyo state was because samples brought from Bodija, Ojoo and Agbowo areas, as well as some farms at Egbeda area of the metropolis tested positive to avian influenza. Hence, farmers whose farms were not affected were sampled from a major live bird market in Ibadan. These farmers gather at Oluyole Estate from several locations including Egbeda, Lagelu and Akiyeyele areas in Ibadan every Monday and Thursday (Figure 1).

Study design

Farms that were not affected by highly pathogenic avian influenza were assessed using a questionnaire-based

Figure 1. Map showing the study area.

cross-sectional study to determine the knowledge, attitude and practices of poultry farmers that could have been predisposed to AI outbreaks. Attempts were made also find the determinants of the avian influenza outbreak.

Sample size determination

Sample size determination

$$N = 1.96^2 P_{ex} (1 - P_{ex}) / d^2.$$

$P_{ex} = 86.0\%$ (proportion of poultry farmers who defined AI correctly) Dairo and Elelu; 2013.

$$N = 1.96 \times 1.96 \times 0.86 \times 0.14 / 0.05^2 = 185.$$

After adjusting for non-response using a rate of 10%, N became 206. Hence the final sample size for this study was 206.

Data collection process

Questionnaires were administered to 206 farmers in order to capture their socio-demographic characteristics, determine their knowledge, attitude and practices (especially bio-security practices) as regards avian influenza. Specific questions on bird/people/material movement, bird health and mortality, personal/environmental hygiene, carcass disposal method, availability of quarantine holding and isolation

facility, health programme, feed and feeding pattern, sharing of farm facilities/ workers, stocking/ restocking and history of being affected during previous outbreaks were used to assess the bio-security practices and also assess their experience of avian influenza signs and symptoms.

Knowledge scoring

The maximum attainable knowledge score was 28 while the cut off value for the knowledge scoring was 14. The knowledge was rated as poor ($X < 14$), average ($X = 14$) and good ($X > 14$). Respondents were grouped into any of these when their mean score falls within any of the score rating.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Poultry production is a very serious business that positively affects the livelihood of farmers in Nigeria when their birds are free of disease. A lot of money is made along the poultry value chain with poultry egg production having the lion share.

Socio-demographic characteristics

Overall, 206 poultry farmers in Ibadan were selected for this study. The mean age was 37.50 ± 4.21 years. Majority (75.2%) were less than 40 years old. Majority were males (67.5%), had tertiary education (80.6%), engaged in livestock keeping as primary occupation (59.2%), rear between less than or 3000 birds presently (73.3%) and have established the poultry farm for not more than 20 years (90.3%). About half of the respondents confirmed the presence of rodents and other farm animals on their farm while 11.2% confirmed to have seen previously seen feral birds in their farms (Table 1).

Bio-security practices

Bird and people movement, bird health and mortality

About one-third (63.3%) of the respondents had recorded sickness in their flock in the last three months. Within the same period, 27% experienced mortality, 22% got new birds, and 46% welcomed visitors who had contact with the birds and holding areas as in (Table 2).

Carcass disposal and holding/quarantine/isolation facility

Three-quarter (75.2%) of the respondents had on-site carcass disposal point.

Major methods of carcass disposal were burning (24.3%), burying (41.6%), throwing into bush (4.9%), and carrying away in trucks (39.3%). Sixty-four percent of the farmers stated that they have quarantine facility, 64% of which conduct quarantine for less than 3 weeks. Three-quarter of our respondents claimed to have isolation facilities which is different from the quarantine facility (Table 3 and Figures 2 - 4).

Personal and environmental hygiene

Eighty-five percent of the farmers selected for this study wash themselves after touching or carrying dead birds. About half washed their clothes and three-quarter their implements after touching or carrying dead birds. Fifty-six percent claimed they have a rodent control programme on the farm (Table 4).

Feeding and health programme

Eighty-five percent of the farmers deliver feed to the farm themselves, about one-third have other people who keeps bird in the neighbourhood while more than 70% vaccinated all their birds, keep their birds in-doors, disinfect their farm regularly and obtained feed from mills that follow adequate bio security and quality control procedures (Table 5).

Sharing of farm facilities/ workers and restocking/stocking

Only eleven farms (5.3%) share farm attendants with other farms while 34(16.6%) share their farming utilities/facilities. Forty (19.4%) of the farms had previously experienced avian influenza outbreaks, 78% of which restocked in less than six months after the outbreaks (Table 6).

Experience of avian influenza signs and symptoms

The most commonly experienced signs of avian influenza in the farms owned by our respondents were diarrhoea (86.4%), drastic decline in egg production (88.3%) swollen comb and wattles (79.6%). Others were loss of appetite (34.5%), sudden death (22.8%) and difficulty in breathing (42.2%) (Table 7).

Knowledge

Poultry farmers in Ibadan displayed a good knowledge of

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents.

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Age		
<40	155	75.2
40-54	41	19.9
>54	10	4.9
Sex		
Male	139	67.5
Female	67	32.5
Highest educational level		
None	20	9.7
Secondary school	20	9.7
Tertiary education	166	80.6
Primary occupation		
Civil servant	40	19.4
Trading	44	21.4
Live stock keeping	122	59.2
No of birds on farm		
<1000	44	21.4
1000-3000	107	51.9
>3000	55	26.7
For how long has the farm established? (years)		
<10	143	69.4
10-20	43	20.9
>20	20	9.7
Variables		
Other animals on farm premises		
Yes	111	53.9
No	95	46.1
Are there rodents on farm?		
Yes	122	59.2
No	84	40.8

Table 2. Bird and people movement, bird health and mortality.

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Has bird sickness increased in the last 3 months?		
Yes	75	36.4
No	151	63.3
Has bird mortality increased in the last 3 months?		
Yes	55	26.7
No	131	73.3
Did you introduce new birds in the last three days?		
Yes	45	21.8
No	161	78.2
Did any of your bird leave the farm premises within this period?		
Yes	10	6.9
No	135	93.1
Did any visitor have contact with birds and holding area?		
Yes	95	46.1
No	111	53.9

Table 3. Isolation and quarantine facility.

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Do you have an isolation pen different from your quarantine facility		
Yes	153	74.3
No	53	25.7
For how long do you quarantine your birds?		
<3 weeks	98	64.1
>3weeks	65	35.9

Figure 2. Carcass disposal and holding/quarantine /isolation facility.

Figure 3. Approximate distance of the carcass disposal point to the regular point.

Figure 4. Method of carcass disposal.

Figure 5. Presence of quarantine facility.

causes, transmission and signs of avian influenza. The mean knowledge score was 18.8 out of a maximum attainable score of 28 (Table 8). This mean score was greater than the average rating score which serves as the cut-off for knowledge (14.0). Furthermore, all the farmers knew that AI can spread from chicken to humans, eating chicken and egg that is not properly cooked can transmit avian influenza, and believed that butchers, children, poultry workers, and bird sellers. Most farmers also knew that the use of PPEs like apron, gloves, face mask, and gloves will prevent infection and spread of AI. About 95% were sure that AI is not transmitted through unprotected

sex. However, a fairly large proportion of the respondents (45-55%) do not know that AI is an infectious communicable disease that can affect all species of bird, caused by a virus and that contact with migratory birds can spread AI. Symptoms of AI correctly identified by the poultry farmers are sudden death (100.0%), bloody diarrhoea (100.0%), drastic decline in egg production (67.0%) and swollen combs (52.4%). The attitude of the poultry farmers regarding AI related issues is poor (Tables 9 -11). Though all of them will not want to buy poultry products from infected farms and agreed that cohabiting with poultry can predispose to AI infection.

Table 4. Personal and environmental hygiene.

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Do you wash yourself after touching or carrying dead birds?		
Yes	175	85.0
No	31	15.0
Do you wash your hands after touching or carrying dead birds?		
Yes	175	85.0
No	31	15.0
Do you wash your clothes after touching or carrying dead birds?		
Yes	108	52.4
No	98	47.5
Do you wash your implements after touching or carrying dead birds?		
Yes	151	74.3
No	55	25.7
Do you have a program for controlling rodents on the farm?		
Yes	117	56.8
No	89	43.2

Table 5. Feeding and health programme

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
How is feed delivered to your farm?		
By self	175	85.0
By feed company	31	15.0
Do other people keep birds in your Neighbourhood?		
Yes	74	35.9
No	132	64.1
Does feed mill follow adequate bio security and quality control procedure?		
Yes	145	70.4
No	61	29.6
Are all your birds vaccinated?		
Yes	153	74.3
No	53	25.7
Do you keep your birds indoors (in facilities, sheds) only?		
Yes	161	68.9
No	45	31.1
Do you regularly disinfect your farm?		
Yes	165	80.1
No	41	19.9

Table 6. Sharing of farm facilities/workers and restocking/stocking

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Do you share your farm attendants with other farms?		
Yes	11	5.3
No	195	94.7
Do you share your farming utilities/facilities with other farms?		
Yes	34	16.5
No	172	83.5
Have you ever experienced African influenza outbreak on your farm?		
Yes	40	19.4
No	166	80.6
If yes, how long did it take you to restock after outbreak?		
<6 months	31	77.5
>6months	9	22.5

about half stated they cannot be infected with AI when they eat poultry products during an outbreak, while 60-75% disagreed that slaughtering birds without adequate protection can predispose to AI infection and agreed that

they cannot be infected with AI because I cook for a lengthy period, can rear pigs very close to or on poultry farm and also rear chicken and turkey together in the same pen. The predictors of high AI knowledge among

Table 7. Have you ever experienced any of the following signs on your farm?

Variables	Frequency	Percentages
Sudden death		
Yes	47	22.8
No	159	77.2
Loss of appetite		
Yes	71	34.5
No	135	65.5
Diarrhoea		
Yes	178	86.4
No	28	13.6
Difficulty in breathing		
Yes	87	42.2
No	119	57.8
Drastic decline in egg production		
Yes	182	88.3
No	24	11.7
Swollen comb and wattles		
Yes	164	79.6
No	42	20.4

Table 8. Knowledge

	Yes (%)	No (%)
Avian Influenza (AI) is a disease of chicken only.	70(34.0)	136(66.0)
AI is an infectious communicable disease that can affect all species of bird.	132(64.1)	74(35.9)
AI can spread from chicken to humans.	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
AI is caused by a virus.	94(54.4)	112(45.6)
Contact with migratory birds can.	98(47.6)	108(52.4)
AI can be transmitted through		
Contact with secretions of infected poultry	100(48.5)	106(51.5)
Eating chicken that is not properly cooked	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Unprotected sexual intercourse	12(5.8)	194(94.2)
Eating eggs that are not properly cooked	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Handshake.	0(0.0)	206(100.0)
Who are those are majorly at risk of contacting AI?		
Butchers	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Poultry workers	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Bird sellers in live bird market.	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Everybody	40(19.4)	166(80.6)
Little children	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Veterinarian	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Which of these is appropriate for preventing infection and spread of AI?		
Use of apron	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Use of gloves	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Use of face mask	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Use of boots	206(100.0)	0(0.0)

Table 9. Knowledge of symptoms of avian influenza in birds.

Symptom	Yes (%)	No (%)
Sudden death	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Loss of appetite	84(40.8)	122(59.2)
Difficulty in breathing	40(19.4)	166(80.6)
Diarrhoea	77(37.4)	129(62.6)
Bloody diarrhea.	206(100.0)	0(0.0)
Coughing	108(52.4)	98(47.6)
Drastic decline in egg production	138(67.0)	68(33.0)
Swollen combs	108(52.4)	98(47.6)

Table 10. Attitude of poultry workers to avian influenza.

	A (%)	U (%)	D (%)
I cannot be infected with AI when I eat poultry products after hearing there is an outbreak.	64(31.1)	37(18.0)	105(51.0)
I will not buy poultry products from infected farms.	206(100.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
Slaughtering birds without adequate protection can predispose to AI infection	28(13.6)	40(19.4)	138(67.0)
I cannot be infected with AI because I cook for a lengthy period.	145(70.4)	61(29.6)	0(0.0)
I can rear pigs very close to or on poultry farm	158(76.7)	0(0.0)	48(23.3)
Cohabiting with poultry can predispose to AI infection.	206(100.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)
I can rear chicken and turkey together in the same pen.	191(92.7)	0(0.0)	15(7.3)

Table 11. Descriptive statistics of AI knowledge score of poultry farmers in Ibadan.

Variable	Minimum score	Maximum score	Mean ± SD	Average rating	scale	Frequency (%)
Knowledge	16	25	18.8 ± 2.0	14	>14	206(100.0)

poultry farmers are age (p = 0.01), education (p = 0.05), occupation (p = 0.03), No of birds present on the farm (p = 0.05), and years of farm establishment (p = 0.05).

Conclusion

Farmers in Oyo state have good knowledge about the avian influenza. However, educated individuals were better informed about best practices and hence compliance with best bio-security practices would be ensured and/or guaranteed. Farms owned by older people are about 3 times more likely to experience outbreak because they may not be aware of latest trends in managing farm bio-security. Those owned by males are about 2.5 times less likely because males have been proven to be quite energetic thereby allowing them to be able to discharge their duties with vigor. Also, farms owned by uneducated people and those without carcass disposal and quarantine facilities are about 5.4, 2.2, and 1.3 times more likely to suffer from an AI outbreak.

Study limitation

Total refusal of some farmers to participate was a serious limitation.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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